

USE OF ELECTRO-RHEOLOGICAL FLUIDS FOR DAMPING CONTROL OF CFRP BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

Smart composite beams consisting of two CFRP plates and an Electro-Rheological (ER) fluid layer are constructed. The composite beams having three kinds of fiber orientations and ER fluids with two different particle volume fractions are prepared. Damping properties of the beams are experimentally and theoretically investigated as a function of the applied electric field. Two methods are used for the analysis of the loss factor obtained from the experiments. One is Ross-Kerwin-Unger analysis. In another analysis, the loss factor obtained from the ratio of the total loss strain energy to the storage one of beams is used. The latter analysis shows the better agreement with experimental results than the former.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, much attention has been paid to studies of smart composite structures which have sensors and actuators in order to adapt external stimuli. In smart structures, actuator materials play an important role in the structural control. One of candidates for actuator materials is electro-rheological (ER) fluids.

ER fluids consist of suspension of fine semiconducting particles in a dielectric liquid and the apparent viscosity and rheological properties of ER fluids can be varied by applied electrical field. Viscosity and rheological properties can be varied in a wide range and response time is very short, as short as several milliseconds and this change is reversible[1]. These features are useful for real-time controlling damping properties. Use of ER fluids for damping control has been reported by several researchers[2-7]. Some of them discuss a method for constructing composite beams which consist of outer conductive plates and ER fluids layers. As outer conductive plates, metal plates are mostly used, while few carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) laminated plates are used[3].

In the present study, composite beams consisting of CFRP laminates used for outer conductive plates and an ER fluids layer are constructed. In composite beams, the ER fluids layer is sealed by a silicone rubber in the same manner as proposed by Choi et al.[2]. Composite beams

having three kinds of fiber orientations in CFRP laminated plates and different volume particle fractions in ER fluids are prepared. The damping properties of composite beams are measured experimentally by forced vibration tests with several different intensities of A.C. electric field applied to ER fluids.

SPECIMEN

A specimen is schematically shown in Fig. 1. The specimen consists of two CFRP laminated plates (Toray T300/#2500) and an ER fluids layer(Nippon Shokubai TX-ER2062,TX-ER2064). Three kinds of CFRP laminates having different fiber orientations ($[0^\circ]_4, [+30^\circ/-30^\circ]_3, [+45^\circ/-45^\circ]_3$) are prepared. And two kinds of ER fluids having different particle volume fractions of

Figure 1. Schematical view of a specimen.

Figure 2. Complex moduli properties of ER fluids.

are used. The ER fluids having larger particle volume fraction of are called as ER1 and those having lower one are called as ER2. The particle volume fraction of ER1 is two times larger than that of ER2. The complex moduli versus shear strain of two kinds of ER fluids are shown in Fig. 2. In this figure, it is found that ER1 has larger ER effects than ER2, that is, the larger volume fraction of particles, the larger ER effects. The specimens are 200mm in length and 20mm in width. The thickness of CFRP laminate is 0.5mm and that of ER fluids layer is 0.2mm. In the specimens, ER fluids are filled between two CFRP laminated plates and sealed by a silicone rubber. CFRP laminated plates are used for electrodes to apply electric fields to ER fluids, since CFRP laminate is a conductive material.

EXPERIMENT

The experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 3. This experimental system consists of a random noise generator, a shaker, a non-contacting laser displacement pick-up, an accelerometer, an FFT analyzer and a high voltage A.C. power supply unit. The specimen was supported on the shaker under the clamped-free condition. It was excited by the random force. The displacement of the free end of specimen was measured by the non-contacting laser displacement pick-up and that of fixed end was obtained from integrating twice the acceleration that was measured by the accelerometer. Both data of displacements were saved and an amplitude ratio of the displacement of free end to that of fixed end was calculated by the FFT analyzer. The loss factor was obtained from the half-power bandwidth method applied to the transfer function. The electric fields were provided to the ER fluids by the high voltage A.C. power supply unit. The experiment was conducted at room temperature.

Figure 3. Experimental set-up.

ANALYSIS

Method 1

First, Ross-Kerwin-Ungar analysis[8] is adopted in order to calculate the loss factor of the composite beam containing ER fluids. This analysis (usually referred to as the RKU analysis) has been developed for a three layer system and is usually used to handle both extensional and shear types of treatment.

The flexural rigidity, B^* , of the three-layer system of Fig. 4a is given by

$$B^* = \frac{E_1^* H_1^3}{6} + (E_3^* H_3 H_{31}) \left(\frac{g^*}{1+2g^*} \right) \quad (1)$$

where

$$g^* = \frac{G_2^* L^2}{E_3^* H_3 H_2 \xi_n^2} \quad \text{and} \quad H_{31} = \frac{H_1 + H_3}{2} + H_2$$

$$(H_1 = H_3 = 0.5\text{mm}, H_2 = 0.2\text{mm}, \xi_n = 3.516, L = 200\text{mm})$$

In this equation, E^* is the Young's modulus, G_2^* is the shear modulus of ER fluids, H is the thickness and ξ_n is the n th eigenvalue. Subscript 1 refers to the base structure, subscript 2 to the ER fluids layer, subscript 3 to the constraining layer, and no subscript refers to the composite system. The loss factor of composite system is calculated from the imaginary part and the real part of flexural rigidity given by Eqn (1). In the RKU analysis, the effect of silicone rubber on damping properties of composite beam can not be considered and is neglected. The values of complex moduli of ER fluids are also assumed as constant though they have shear strain dependency as shown in Fig. 2. Here the values at the free end of the beam will be used for the calculation of complex moduli mentioned above.

Figure 4a. Side view of specimen.

Figure 4b. Top view of specimen.

Method 2

Secondly, the loss factor of the composite beam is calculated based on the concept of strain energy. That is, the loss factor is given by the ratio of the loss strain energy to the storage energy of the complex system as illustrated in Figs. 4a and 4b. In this case, both influence of silicone rubber and strain dependency of ER fluids can be considered. In the calculation, the loss and storage strain energies are summarized for constituent materials such as CFRP, ER fluids and silicone rubber. Thus, the following equation is given for the loss factor of the composite beam.

$$\eta = \frac{\sum U''_{CFRP} + \sum U''_{ER} + \sum U''_{Silicon}}{\sum U'_{CFRP} + \sum U'_{ER} + \sum U'_{Silicon}} \quad (2)$$

where U'' is the loss strain energy and U' , the storage one. Subscripts such as CFRP, ER, Silicone mean constituent materials of the composite beam.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 5 shows the variation of the amplitude ratio of a specimen as changing applied electric field intensity, where $[0^\circ]_4$ CFRP laminates and ER1 were used. In this figure, it is found that the peak values of amplitude ratio are clearly reduced by increasing applied electric field intensity and frequencies where the amplitude ratio indicates its peak value are slightly increased. This reveals that adopting ER fluids to composite beams is much effective for controlling their vibration characteristics subjected to the external stimuli of the electric field.

The loss factor was experimentally obtained from the curves of amplitude ratio using the half-power bandwidth method. The loss factors of composite beams treated in the present study are

Figure 5. Effects of electric field intensity on damping properties, where $[0^\circ]_4$ CFRP laminates and ER1 are used.

obtained as illustrated in Fig. 6. This figure shows that composite beams containing ER1 have the better damping properties than ones with ER2. This is due to the reason why ER1 has the larger ER effects than ER2 as shown in Fig. 2. It is also found that the loss factors of composite beams are larger as the fiber orientation angle increases.

Figs. 7a-7c present the comparison between calculated values and experimental values of loss factor for composite beams using ER1. From these results, it is found that the calculated loss factors by using Method 1 are much larger than the experimental values. And the difference

Figure 6. Loss factor of composite beams versus intensity of electric fields.

Figure 7a. Comparison of calculated values with experimental values for loss factors, where $[0^\circ]_4$ CFRP laminates and ER1 are used.

Figure 7b. Comparison of calculated values with experimental values for loss factors, where $[+30^{\circ}/-30^{\circ}]_s$ CFRP laminates and ER1 are used.

Figure 7c. Comparison of calculated values with experimental values for loss factors, where $[+45^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}]_s$ CFRP laminates and ER1 are used.

between them is larger as the fiber orientation angles increase. This reason is supposed that the storage energy of silicone rubber increases in comparison of that of CFRP laminate as the fiber orientation angle increases.

On the other hand, the results obtained by using Method 2 show the better agreement with experimental value. This good agreement is due to the fact that the influence of silicone rubber and the strain dependency of ER fluids on damping properties of composite beam are considered. Because, as there is a silicone rubber in the gap between two CFRP laminates, the strain of silicone rubber may be as same as that of ER fluids. Hence, the amount of strain energy in silicone rubber is not enough small to be neglected.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, it has been shown that damping properties of CFRP composites beams including ER fluids can be controlled by changing the intensity of electric fields applied to the CFRP electrodes.

The results obtained here are summarized as follows;

- (1) ER fluids are much effective for controlling the damping properties of composite beam.
- (2) The particle volume fractions of ER fluids influence damping properties of composite beams. That is, ER fluids having larger particle volume fraction are more effective for improving damping properties of the composite beam.
- (3) Changing fiber orientations of CFRP laminates can produce composite beams having variational damping properties. The damping properties of composite beam increase as the fiber orientation angle increases.
- (4) The calculated values of loss factor based on the total strain energy of constituent materials show the better agreement with the experimental values than those using RKU analysis do. This result means that the RKU analysis is less applicable since the strain energy of silicone rubber and the strain dependency of ER fluids affect the damping properties of composite beam.

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REFERENCES

1. M. V. Gandhi and B. S. Thompson, Smart materials and structures, Chapter 4, Electro-rheological fluids, Chapman & Hall, (1993).
2. Y. Choi, A. F. Sprecher and H. Conrad, Vibration characteristics of a composite beam containing an electrorheological fluid, *J. of Intell. Mater. Syst. and Struct.*, **1**, 91-104 (1990).
3. S. B. Choi, B. S. Thompson and M. V. Gandhi, An experimental investigation on smart laminated composite structures featuring embedded electro-rheological fluid domains for vibration-control applications, *Composites Engineering*, **2**, Nos 5-7, 543-559, (1992).
4. S. Morishita, T. Ura, ER fluid applications to vibration control devices and an adaptive neural-net controller, *J. of Intell. Mater. Syst. and Struct.*, **4**, 366-372, Jul (1993).
5. G. Haiqing, L. M. King and T. B. Cher, Influence of a locally applied electro-rheological fluid layer on vibration of a simple cantilever beam, *J. of Intell. Mater. Syst. and Struct.*, **4**, 379-384, Jul (1993).
6. Y. Chen, F.-G. Yuan and H. Conrad, Damping characteristics of laminate composites containing electrorheological (ER) fluids, *Proc. of ICIM'94*, 328-339, (1994).
7. W. Kordonsky, A. Matsepuro, S. Demchuk and Z. Novikora, Electrorheological fluid-based composite materials properties for vibration control in distributed systems, *Proc. of ICIM '94*, 743-750, (1994).
8. Ahid D., Nashif, David I. G., Jones, and John P., Henderson, Vibration damping, Chapter 6, Surface damping treatment, New York, John Wiley & Sons, 1985